

THE IMPACT OF PHOSPHORUS-ENRICHED FARMYARD MANURE AND ARBUSCULAR MYCORRHIZA ON MACRONUTRIENT REMOVAL BY SORGHUM

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Abstract

A field study was conducted to evaluate the impact of phosphorus-enriched farmyard manure and arbuscular mycorrhiza (AM) on macronutrient removal by sorghum during rabi season in the years 2016-17, 2017-18 and 2018-19 at Main Sugarcane Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari, Gujarat. The application of different phosphorus treatments to the soil through SSP, enriched FYM with or without arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi affected the sorghum's uptake of N, P, and K substantially. The soil was an Inceptisol, medium in available P. Different phosphorus treatments increased grain and stalk yields in all the three years. The uptake of macronutrient elements accordingly increased with the increase in yield. Phosphorus treatments also increased the nutrient harvest index for macronutrient elements. Ratio of nutrient concentrations in the grain relative to stalk was widest for N (3.06:1) and narrowest for K (0.22:1).

Keywords: Sorghum, phosphorus-enriched farmyard manure, arbuscular mycorrhiza, macronutrient uptake, nutrient harvest index

Introduction

Millets, sometimes known as "nutri-grains," are small-grained cereals. Millets of many kinds, including pearl millet, sorghum, finger millet, foxtail millet, proso millet, barnyard millet, kodo millet, and tiny millet, are produced in India. The only two of these that are widely grown in the nation are sorghum and pearl millet; the other millets are categorised as minor or little millets. Sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench) is the fifth most significant crop in the world, ranking behind maize, rice, wheat, and barley (Balakrishna *et al.*, 2019)^[1]. Compared to other cereals, it needs less water and can survive more weather variations. In India, it is cultivated in an area of about 4.96 millions hectares with a total production of about 998 kg/ha. In Gujarat, about 0.09 million hectares area is under sorghum cultivation with total production of 0.09 million tonnes (Louhar *et al.*, 2020)^[2]. It is cultivated in almost all districts of the state. The Main Sorghum Research Station is located at Surat. Sorghum is a demanding crop that needs enough nutrition; the proper fertilizers must be used if any nutrients are found to be deficient. Depending on the region, soil type, prior crop, and fertilizer history, different fertilizer rates will apply. The nutrients nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) are the ones that frequently restrict output. In some soils or growing environments, sulphur (S), potassium (K), and zinc (Zn) may also be limiting elements. Phosphorus affect early growth of young sorghum by facilitating early root formation and growth, enhancing photosynthesis, respiration, energy storage and transfer, cell division, and expansion. It also improves water use efficiency. The majority of Indian soils are either P-deficient or P-insignificant. Hence, adequate P fertilization is necessary for sustaining and economically viable crop production. High doses of phosphatic fertilizer, which must be imported and is expensive, are necessary for phosphorus-deficient soils. The finding of multiple rock phosphate (RP) deposits throughout the nation has substantially increased interest in using this local substance as an alternative to phosphatic fertilizers. In this context, arbuscular mycorrhizae (AM) and their function in the uptake of immobile nutrients from the soil, such as phosphorus, have long been known and well documented. The effect of AM is thought to be caused by three

main mechanisms: (i) increased soil volume exploitation by the hyphal network, which reduces the diffusion pathway by extending the active absorption surface and opening access to areas ordinarily inaccessible to roots (ii) A stronger affinity for phosphate in hyphae, as indicated by a lower K_m value in the Michaelis-Menten equation; (iii) the ability of hyphae to absorb P at lower solution concentrations than the roots themselves; and (iv) AM-induced rhizosphere alterations, such as acid or chelate exudation (Berruti *et al.*, 2016)^[3]. Determining the effects of phosphorus-enriched farmyard manure (enriched FYM) on the amount of crude protein and the assimilation of N, P, and K by sorghum is therefore the purpose of the study. Together with saving valuable foreign currency and reducing reliance on pricey inorganic phosphate fertilizers, this would also solve waste management issues in a way that is both ethical and practical from an economic standpoint.

Materials and Methods

The field experiment was conducted at the Main Sugarcane Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari during Rabi in the year 2016-17, 2017-18 and 2018-19 to study the effect of phosphorus enriched farmyard manure and arbuscular mycorrhiza on macronutrient removal by sorghum. The soils of experimental site were Inceptisol and clay in texture, slightly alkaline (pH 7.8) in reaction, high in organic carbon (0.78 %), low with respect to available nitrogen (267.00 kg/ha), medium available phosphorus (35.56 kg/ha) and high in available potassium (428 kg/ha). The treatments for the study consisted of viz, Absolute Control, 100% P as Enriched FYM, 100% P as SSP, 75% P as Enriched FYM + AM (arbuscular mycorrhiza) @100g/acre, 75% P as SSP +AM @100g/acre, 50 % P as Enriched FYM+ AM @100g/acre and 50% P as SSP+AM @100g/acre, which replicated for three times in randomized block design. Sorghum variety GJ 38 sown keeping row to row distance 45 cm with recommended seed rate (12 kg/ha). The numbers of rows were 8 in gross plot of 3.6 m x 5 m size. Enriched FYM was applied as per treatment about a week before sowing. The recommended dose of fertilizer for the sorghum is 80:40:0 kg/ha N: P₂O₅:K₂O. The nitrogen was applied through urea (46% N) whereas phosphorus was applied through single

superphosphate (16% P₂O₅) and Enriched FYM was applied as basal on the base of 8% total phosphorus content. Enriched FYM was prepared by mixing rock phosphate and FYM in 1:15 ratio along with PSB (*Bacillus megatherium*) for 45 day. The 50% dose of nitrogen and full dose of phosphorus were applied at the time of sowing; remaining half dose of nitrogen was applied after thirty days of sowing. Arbuscular mycorrhiza (*Glomus intraradis*) containing 3000 IP /g @ 100g /acre was applied at the time of sowing in respective treatments. A common dose of organic manures (bio-compost @ 15 t/ha) applied to all treatments before sowing and evenly spread and mixed in that

particular bed. Bio-compost and enriched FYM was analyzed for NPK and micronutrient content and is represented in Table 1. The plant sample (seed and straw) of sorghum were collected from each plot and were dried for 48 hours in hot air oven at 65 ± 5°C. These dried samples were partitioned into grain and straw. Finally ground samples were passed through 0.5 mm mesh sieve and were used for chemical determination of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium concentration as described by Jackson (1973)^[4]. The total respective nutrient uptake by sorghum from each treatment was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Total nutrient uptake } \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{ha}}\right) = \text{Nutrient uptake by seed } \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{ha}}\right) + \text{Nutrient uptake by straw } \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{ha}}\right)$$

$$\text{Nutrient uptake by seed } \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{ha}}\right) = \frac{\text{Nutrient content in seed (percent)} \times \text{seed yield } \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{ha}}\right)}{100}$$

$$\text{Nutrient uptake by straw } \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{ha}}\right) = \frac{\text{Nutrient content in seed (percent)} \times \text{Straw dry matter yield } \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{ha}}\right)}{100}$$

$$\text{Nutrient harvest index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Amount in grain}}{\text{Amount in grain and salk}} \times 100$$

The observed data was subjected to statistical analysis as described by Panse and Sukhatme (1978)^[5].

Results and Discussion

Sorghum responded spectacularly to different P treatments in each of the three years and in pooled analysis. Significantly higher grain yield was recorded with the application of 75% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre (5.13 t/ha) in the year 2016-17 which was at par with 100% P as enriched FYM (4.38 t/ha), 75% P as enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre (4.30 t/ha), 50% P as enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre (4.41 t/ha) and 50% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre (4.26 t/ha). However, in second and third year of experiment treatment 100% P as SSP (3.99 q/ha, 3.67t/ha) recorded significantly higher grain yield which was statistically at par with 100% P as enriched FYM (3.73 t/ha) and 75% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre (3.84 t/ha) during the year 2017-18 and with 75% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre (3.16 t/ha) during the year 2018-19. Treatment 75% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre (4.04 t/ha) statistically at par with 100% P as enriched FYM (3.59 t/ha), 100% P as SSP (3.62 t/ha), 75% P as enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre (3.66 t/ha) and 50% P as enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre (4.41 t/ha) (3.33 t/ha) in pooled result. The data on grain yield of sorghum expressed that the application of phosphorus fertilizer either SSP, P enriched FYM alone or along with AM increased significantly grain yield over control during the three years of the study and with respect to pooled analysis.

The results showed that the different treatments had significant influence on stalk yield during three years of experimentation and also in pooled analysis. Significantly higher stalk yield was recorded under the treatment 75% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre (7.03 t/ha) during year 2016-17 which was at par with 100% P as enriched FYM (6.18 t/ha), 75% P as enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre (6.08 t/ha), 50% P as enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre (4.41 q/ha) (6.09 t/ha) and 50% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre (5.92 t/ha). However, in second and third year of experiment treatment 100% P as SSP (5.63 q/ha, 5.12 t/ha) recorded significantly higher stalk yield which was statistically at par with 100% P as enriched FYM (5.28 t/ha) 75% P as enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre (5.17 t/ha) and 75% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre (5.11 t/ha) during the year 2017-18. Treatment 75% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre (5.57 t/ha) recorded statistically at par with 100% P as enriched FYM (5.07 t/ha), 100% P as SSP (5.07 t/ha) and 75% P as enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre (5.19 t/ha) in pooled result. Interaction between years to treatment statistically was non-significant. Based on the pooled statistical analysis of the three years data, sorghum grain yield increased from 1.79 to 4.04 t/ha and the stalk yield increased from 2.51 to 5.57 t/ha with application of 75% P as

SSP+AM@100g/acre. The uptake of macro nutrients increased in response to increased yields of grain and stalk (Table 2). The total amounts of different nutrients harvested in the biomass followed the decreasing order: K > N > P. On an average, with the application of 75% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre, total N uptake increased 2.1 times, P uptake 2.76 times, and K uptake 2.19 times that of uptake in control plots. This might be explained by the fact that additional phosphorus raised the concentration of N and P in grain and stalk by fostering a healthy internal nutrient environment and enhancing photosynthetic efficiency, both of which promoted plant development and crop yield. The increased grain and stalk output, along with higher NPK content, led to improved uptake of these nutrients since nutrient uptake is a function of dry matter (grain and stalk) and nutrient content. Most of the K remain in the stalk and only small portions were translocated to the grain. But for N and P, larger amounts were found in the grain than in the stalk. Ratio of nutrient concentrations in the grain relative to stalk varied widely. The ratios of nutrient concentrations in the grain to stalk were 3.06: 1 for N, 2.06:1 for P, and 0.22:1 for K. The results imply that under a farming practice in which the sorghum stalks are returned to the land, they would replenish soil fertility at least partly with regard to nutrient such as K. Sorghum stalk application, however, will return small amount of P and the smallest amount of N. The amounts of major nutrients removed in the biomass to produce 1 tonne of sorghum grain, K accounted for the highest amount (23.48 kg) followed by N (14.44 kg), and P (6.27 kg). It is possible that high level of K measured in the present study may not be required for optimum crop production, and represent luxury consumption because the soil was is rich in K. Plant nutrient harvest indicis (amount in grain/amount in grain and stalk) for macronutrient elements were greatly increased by different P fertilization of the crop (Table 3). The enhanced NPK harvest the application of SSP, enriched FYM, and AM fungus, which in turn promoted and boosted root growth and early vegetative growth, increasing photosynthetic activity in the plant. This may have encouraged both the functioning and expansion of the roots, leading to a greater uptake of nutrients from the soil environment by roots and fungal hyphae extensions. indicis may be attributable to the soil's increased phosphorus content initially higher availability of nutrients, as a result of The findings of Sahrawat *et al.* (1998)^[6], Rathore and Singh (1999)^[7], Jibrin *et al.* (2002)^[8], and Noor (2008)^[9], are consistent with the improved nutritional uptake with P treatment without or with mycorrhiza inoculation.

Conclusion

It is well known that the concentration of nutrients at the cellular level and the formation of dry matter are both necessary for nutrient accumulation. Hence, the combined effects of phosphorous fertilization and arbuscular mycorrhiza ultimately resulted in better nutrient uptake by the crop as well as higher nutrient accumulation by the plant. This study shows that P enriched FYM, which is made by mixing low-grade rock phosphate with arbuscular mycorrhiza can be a viable technology for managing biodegradable waste, such as crop residue, and the efficient use of non-renewable sources of phosphorus in crop production, which can help to reduce the reliance on expensive chemical fertilizers and, consequently, huge amounts of foreign exchange. Future study should focus on the assessment and commercial manufacture of the product utilizing a variety of renewable resources and test the performance of the product in farmers' fields under diverse soil and crop conditions in order to make P enriched FYM commercially profitable to farmers.

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References

1. **K. Archana, T. Prabhakar Reddy, T. Anjaiah and B. Padmaja 2018**, Effect Of Levels Of Phosphorus And Its Time Of Application On Soil Nutrient Status And Yield Of Rice Grown On P Accumulated Soil, Vol. VIII, Issue Special(C) , August 2018 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, 299-302.
2. **Balakrishna D, Vinodh R, Madhu P, Avinash S, Rajappa PV, Bhat BV 2019**,. Tissue culture and genetic transformation in Sorghum bicolor. In Breeding Sorghum for diverse end uses 2019 Jan 1 (pp. 115-130). Woodhead Publishing.
3. **Louhar GA, Bana RS, Kumar VI, Kumar H. 2020**, Nutrient management technologies of millets for higher productivity and nutritional security. Indian J. Agric. Sci. 2020 Dec 1; 90:2243-50.
4. **Berruti A, Lumini E, Balestrini R, Bianciotto V. 2016**, Arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi as natural biofertilizers: let's benefit from past successes. Frontiers in microbiology. 2016 Jan 19; 6:1559.

5. Jackson ML. Soil chemical analysis prentice Hall. Inc., Englewood Cliffs, NJ. 1958; 498:183-204.
6. **Panase VG and Sukhatme PV. 1978**, Statistical Methods for Agricultural Workers, I. C. A. R., New Delhi, India, 1978.
7. **Sahrawat KL, Rego TJ, Rahman MH, Rag JK. 1998**, Phosphorus response effects on macro- and micronutrient removal by sorghum under rainfed cropping on a vertisol. Journal of the Indian Society of Soil Science. 1998;46(1):58-60.
8. **Rathore VP, Singh HP. 1999**, Influence of vesicular-arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi and phosphate on maize. Journal of the Indian Society of Soil Science. 1999;43(2):207-10.
9. **Jibrin JM, Chude VO, Horst WJ, Amapu IY. 2002**, Effect of cover crops, lime and rock phosphate on maize (*Zea mays* L.) in an acidic soil of Northern Guinea Savanna of Nigeria. Journal of Agriculture and Rural Development in the Tropics and Subtropics (JARTS). 2002;103(2):169-76.
10. **K. S. Bharadkar*, B. S. Indulkar, P. B. Adsul, P. M. Ghodke 2019**, Interactive Effect Of Phosphate Solubilizing Microorganisms And Phosphorus Levels On Yield and Quality Of Cowpea (*Vigna Unguiculata* L.) In Inceptisol, Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxx, Oct 2021 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, pp 159-161
11. **Noor A. 2008**, Improvement of Soil Chemistry Characteristic of Upland with Rock Phosphate, Phosphate-Solubilizing Bacteria and Farm Yard Manure for Increase of Soybean Yield. Journal of Tropical Soils. 2008 Jan 1;13(1):49-58.
12. **Om Prakash Prajapat1, Surendra Singh2 and Lala Ram Yadav 2023**, Nitrogen, Phosphorus Content And Uptake With Their Interactive Effect On Chickpea (*Cicer Arietinum* L.) As Influenced By Different Liquid Biofertilizers Under Varying Fertility Levels, Vol. Xiii, Issue Xxxxvii, July 2023 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Pp 929-932.
13. **Sayali Sonavane, Ritu Thakare, T.D. Patil and R.D. Chaudhari, 2019**, Enhancement Of Phosphorus Solubility From Rock Phosphate And Nutrient Availability Through Composting With Weeds , Vol. IX, Issue Xxix, April 2019 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, 245-249.

Table 1: Bio-compost and enriched FYM analysis

Particulars	Bio-compost	Enriched FYM
pH	6.28	7.24
EC dS/m	0.51	2.24
Total carbon (%)	34.81	27.71
Total P (%)	0.32	3.03
Total N (%)	1.43	0.48
Total K (%)	1.50	0.90
Fe (%)	0.23	143
Mn (mg/kg)	90.73	85
Zn (mg/kg)	25.37	37.44
Cu (mg/kg)	1.45	13.66

Table 2: Yield and total nutrients harvested in sorghum due to different phosphorus treatments. Results presented are based on the pooled statistical analysis of the three years (2016-17to 2018-19) data analysis

P treatments	Grain (t/ha)	Stalk (t/ha)	Total nutrient harvested (kg/ha)		
			N	P	K
Absolute Control	1.79	2.51	27.02	10.30	42.67
100% P as Enriched FYM	3.59	5.07	50.31	24.37	85.18
100% P as SSP	3.62	5.07	54.69	23.01	88.91
75% P as Enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre	3.66	5.19	52.10	22.04	88.21
75% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre	4.04	5.57	56.82	28.47	93.65
50% P as Enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre	3.33	4.61	49.42	17.89	71.40
50% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre	3.30	4.59	45.33	21.64	77.72
SEm.±	0.22	0.31	5.33	2.22	5.88
CD at 5 %	0.63	0.88	16.43	6.84	16.89

Table 3: Nutrient element harvest index (%) of sorghum as affected by P fertilization

P treatments	Element		
	N	P	K
Absolute Control	66.06	64.17	12.30
100% P as Enriched FYM	63.49	61.14	13.88
100% P as SSP	68.28	59.19	12.32
75% P as Enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre	65.12	59.07	12.16
75% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre	65.54	60.94	13.75
50% P as Enriched FYM+AM@100g/acre	63.25	51.48	11.55
50% P as SSP+AM@100g/acre	65.19	59.84	12.89
Mean	65.28	59.41	12.69